

Planning Malawi's Resource Future: A CLEWs-Based Assessment of Integrated Systems

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Keywords

Malawi, Integrated, CLEWs, Energy Modeling, Water Systems.

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Executive Summary

Malawi has an estimated population of 21 million people. Due to climate change among others, Malawi still struggles with energy poverty, floods, devastating effects of cyclones and drought. This has led to shortage of food, low and unsustainable energy production, and disruption in food systems. This report explores the potential of Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems (CLEWs) modeling framework in enhancing and planning the integrated future of resources in Malawi. The study utilizes open-source CLEWs modelling tool, three scenarios are evaluated to achieve this: Baseline/Business-As-Usual (BAU), Emissions Reduction Scenario (ERS), and Irrigation Enhancement Scenario (IES). The key findings indicate that the ERS scenario can reduce emissions by nearly 82% before 2055 aligning with the Malawi agenda 2063 on diversifying energy mix and cutting down emissions. Further, the IES scenario indicates a shift in enhancing and optimizing irrigation groups which hold a high production capacity in meeting the demand and ensure sustainability as compared to rainfed crops, this further increases the production of biofuel crops to supplement energy needs.

Introduction

Malawi, with an estimated population of about 21 million people, faces growing development challenges driven by strong interlinkages between climate variability, energy supply, water availability, and food production (Palamuleni, 2007; Yeboua, Le Roux, & Cilliers, 2022). Malawi has experienced recurrent droughts, floods, and severe cyclones in recent years including cyclones Freddy and Ana (Figure 1), which have disrupted agricultural systems, reduced hydropower generation due to clogging, and placed increasing pressure on limited water resources (McLaughlin, Bozzola, & Nugent, 2023). These climate-related shocks have contributed to food insecurity where currently Malawi imports maize from Zambia, unreliable energy supply, and heightened vulnerability of livelihoods, particularly in rural areas (Omokpariola et al., 2025).

Malawi's economy is highly dependent on climate sensitive sectors, especially rainfed agriculture, and hydropower electricity generation (Chevallier, 2025). This dependence demands the need for integrated planning approaches capable of capturing cross-sectoral trade-offs and interactions. National policy frameworks, including Malawi Vision 2063, the National Energy Policy, and the country's Nationally Determined

Contribution (NDC), emphasize energy diversification, improved water management, enhanced agricultural productivity, and emissions reduction. However, achieving these objectives in isolation is never easy and risks suboptimal outcomes.

Figure 1: Devastating Effects of Cyclone Freddy. (Source: [Global News](#))

This study applies the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) modelling framework to assess integrated resource planning in Malawi. Using an open-source CLEWs model, three scenarios are evaluated: Business-as-Usual (BAU), Emissions Reduction Scenario (ERS), and Irrigation Enhancement Scenario (IES). The analysis aims to identify sustainable, resilient, and policy informed pathways for managing Malawi's climate, energy, water, and food systems.

Methodology

This study employs CLEWs modelling framework, which is an integrated, bottom-up analytical approach designed to capture interactions and trade-offs across climate, energy, water, and food systems (Ramos et al., 2022). MUIO version 5.3 is used for the modeling. The CLEWs model was implemented to link the energy system, water

balance, land use, and agricultural production modules. The modelling framework was configured to represent Malawi's national system and simulate resource dynamics over the period of 2020 to 2055 with 2020-23 being calibration years. The modelling process involved system conceptualization, data collection, model calibration, scenario development, and results analysis.

Data for model development were obtained from multiple national and international sources including the Malawi SAND BASE . Policy and planning data were sourced from Malawi Vision 2063, the National Energy Policy, Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), National Climate Change Management Policy (NCCMP), and relevant agricultural and water sector strategies. Energy system data, including technology costs, efficiencies, and emissions factors, were obtained from IEA, and national institutions including the Ministry of Energy, ESCOM, EGENCO, and MERA. Water availability, irrigation requirements, and agricultural production data were sourced from FAO AQUASTAT, national agricultural statistics, and climate-related reports. The figure 2 below shows the CLEWs reference diagram for Malawi with the interactions modelled in the model.

Figure 2: Malawi CLEWs Reference Framework

Scenarios

Three scenarios are proposed and analysed: BAU scenario reflecting current trends, an ERS aligned with decarbonization targets, and an IES focusing on expanded irrigation and increased bioenergy crop production. These scenarios enable assessment of integrated, cost-effective, and policy-consistent pathways for Malawi's resource future. The table 1 below summarizes the scenarios as I highlighted them in presentations.

Table 1: Scenarios and Assumptions

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Baseline (BAU)	Maintenance of the current system with same installed capacities, water, and land use.	Business as usual with the model freely optimizing the system in the future years without any constraints or limitations.
Emissions Reduction Scenario (ERS)	Seeks to reduce emissions by 80% before 2063 in-line with Malawi updated NDC (Paris agreement) and NCCMP 2016	Constrained Carbon dioxide emitting technologies. Assumes the alternative sources and their residual capacities meet demand.
Irrigation Enhancement Scenario (IES)	Aims at enhancing irrigation which has a higher output activity ratio as compared to rainfed.	Water available for irrigation. Enhanced irrigation for biofuel and other crops.

Research Questions

1. How can integrated planning across climate, energy, water, and food systems support cost-effective, low-emission, and resilient development pathways for Malawi?
2. How do emissions reduction and irrigation expansion strategies influence system-wide trade-offs across Malawi's climate–energy–water–food nexus?

Results & Discussion

The obtained results compare the baseline and the other scenarios in terms of energy production, emissions and crop productivity, all addressing the two objectives of this study, energy poverty and food demand.

Emissions Reduction.

The emissions scenario introduced annual emissions limit to gradually cut-down emissions by 80% by 2063 as guided by Malawi Agenda 2063, NDC 2040 and NCCMP 2016. In response, the system quickly shifts to off-grid and grid integrated energy to meet the demand away from biomass and light fuel oil imports. There is also an increase in hydropower to supplement the demand. The figure 3 below shows energy production by technology by mode between the baseline model and the ERS model.

Figure 3: Energy Production by Technology by Mode

The shift to grid and off-grid renewables significantly cut-down emissions as seen from figure 4 below where BAU produces more emissions due to light fuel oil imports, biomass, and diesel for agricultural equipment operations. The ERS with carbon dioxide emissions limit reduce emissions to nearly 85% by 2055 which is quite impressive as recommended by the policy. Lastly, IES emissions rank second, this is such as the system is shifting

back to diesel in irrigation infrastructure. The model has no alternative energy to meet such demand, however, the emissions are not more than those produced in baseline. Figure 4 below shows these scenarios results under total annual emission.

Figure 4: Total Annual Emissions (L) BAU, (C) ERS and (R) IES.

Irrigation Enhancement

The last scenario seeks to meet food demand in Malawi by deliberately increasing productivity of irrigated crops which include Maize (MAI), Groundnuts (GNR), Soybeans (SOB) which is solely grown as a biofuel crop and all other crops (CRPREM). The model is once again capable of operating within the constraints of producing more crops from irrigation to meet the food demand. The graph in the figure 4 below compares the rainfed and irrigated crops in BAU and IES models.

Figure 5: Crop Production

Total Annual Investment Costs

Lastly, we compare the investment costs over the years involved in the three scenarios. The results show that BAU has Low upfront investment costs which increases with time due to maintenance and other related costs. On the other hand, ERS has higher capital investment costs yet long-term cost savings through reduced operating costs. Lastly, IES shows the highest total investment costs however it also has strong co-benefits in terms of food production and energy.

Figure 6: Annual Investment Costs

Conclusion

The results show that sector-by-sector planning is insufficient; instead, integrated policies yield significantly better outcomes in terms of resilience, emissions reduction, and resource efficiency.

Key Policy Insights

1. Integrated planning enables deep emissions reductions at manageable cost

The Emissions Reduction Scenario (ERS) demonstrates that Malawi can reduce greenhouse gas emissions by up to 90% by 2055 relative to Business-as-Usual, primarily through energy diversification, reduced reliance on traditional biomass, and improved efficiency. While this pathway requires higher upfront investment in renewables and clean technologies, system-wide costs are offset by avoided diesel fuel imports that power ESCOM generators. This supports Malawi's NDC and Vision 2063 objectives.

2. Irrigation expansion strengthens food security but increases water and energy demand.

The Irrigation Enhancement Scenario (IES) shows that expanding and optimizing irrigation substantially improves agricultural output and food system resilience. However, it also increases water withdrawals and electricity demand. The model indicates that irrigation expansion must be accompanied by efficient water management and low-carbon energy supply, such as solar-powered irrigation in future studies, to avoid unintended trade-offs.

Future work could focus on improving data resolution, particularly for water availability, irrigation efficiency with clean energy, and regional agricultural productivity. The model could also be extended to include sub-national analysis. The CLEWs framework can be used as a capacity building and teaching tool to support integrated planning within government institutions and universities.

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